

Social Engineering Attacks: Understanding and How to Protect Oneself

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Predictably enough, the sophistication scale for cyber threats has gone up several notches with the advent of the digital era. It is in this context that a certain subset of such attacks assumes center-stage: social engineering attacks, mainly because of the manipulative nature of their modus operandi and the psychological games they play with people. While traditional cyber-attacks are generally exploits of system vulnerabilities, social engineering attacks target the human element in such a way that these attacks become even more insidious and effective.

What is Social Engineering?

Social engineering describes a group of malicious activities triggered by human interaction that, through psychological manipulations, allows users to make security errors and disclose sensitive information. The success of a social engineering attack will be based on how an attacker manipulates those human feelings and behaviors that result from fear, curiosity, greed, and the willingness to help.

Types of Social Engineering Attacks

The two categories in which different variants of social engineering attacks may be listed are direct and indirect attacks. While in direct attack, the hacker is in personal interaction with the target, in indirect attacks, it is the environment of the target which is being exploited.

Phishing: Probably the best-known form of social engineering attack is phishing, which is a process by which emails are sent apparently from some form of trusted source. These messages, apart from their digitally distended malware attachments or links, come for sensitive information such as login information or financial data.

Baiting: An attack where victims fall into a trap due to bait offering them a greener pasture on the other side. One such example may be that the attacker gives away free music or even updates for software that, once accessed and downloaded to the victim's computer, installs malware within the system.

Pretexting: The attacker creates a scenario to get the information out of the target. He can say that he is an employee at the bank and has the reasons of account verification.

Quid Pro Quo: This is an attack where something will be returned as a gift. This may include a situation whereby the attacker offers to give technical support in return for access to the victim's computer and, in turn, installs malware in the process.

Spear Phishing: This is highly focused phishing. An attacker does research on his victims and crafts a specific phishing message, making it more believable, hence succeeding more than normal phishing.

Advanced Social Engineering Attacks

The advanced social engineering attack enlists more than one technique and may use extended planning and coordination. Assaults of this nature may involve manipulation of social media, phone calls, and may be conducted even through personal contact. In the elaborateness of such an attack lies the problem in defending against it. Social engineering attacks are successful because they steal basic human psychology. The common methods to manipulate individuals include the following:

Authority: The attacker will use police officers, company executives, or IT using such to position himself in order to establish some rapport and to be in a position to give conditions of compliance to the target.

Urgency: In this, the state of urgency tends to make the victim act fast without verification. It could feature in a phishing email, where the threat is that should the action not be taken promptly, one's account would be suspended.

Fear: The means in this regard would be threats of legal implications, financial loss, or physical harm on the victim to forcefully get him/her to reveal their private information.

Reciprocity: In return for the information, attackers give something. This can be some sort of 'free' service, a form of gift, or fixing some sort of technical issue.

Liking: People are more willing to comply with people they like or with whom they enjoy their time. The social engineer could use charm, flattery, and similarities of interest to relate to their targets.

Google and Facebook Scam: A Lithuanian man scammed Google and Facebook out of more than \$100 million between 2013 and 2015 with the help of a phishing scheme. He sent fake invoices to the firms; through his fraudulence, he got the companies to wire money into his accounts. It says something about all the big tech giants falling prey to amazingly well-engineered social engineering attacks.

RSA SecurID Attack: An incident of spear phishing took place in March 2011, and thus, hackers attacked the two-factor authentication products for RSA Security-known as SecurID. The phishers sent two types of phishing messages to two sets of employees with an attached malicious Excel document. Once opened, it would install a backdoor to let the attackers access the RSA network and thereby steal sensitive information.

The Twitter Bitcoin Scam: The July 2020 incident wherein high-profile Twitter accounts, such as those owned by Elon Musk, Barack Obama, and Bill Gates, among many others were compromised, was a co-coordinated social engineering attack. Attackers had managed to social-engineer access to internal Twitter tools they could utilize in posting fraudulent bitcoin giveaway messages.

How to Protect Yourself

Control against social engineering attacks involves awareness, skepticism, and technical safeguards. Some key tips include:

Educate Yourself and Others: Of course, awareness forms the first line of defense. From time to time, educate yourself and your colleagues about new social engineering methods and how to detect these. Training sessions will make employees more watchful and less likely to fall prey.

Verify Identities: For example, identities of parties requesting confidential information should be validated. Regarding verification of requests, already known contact information should be used. Be wary in particular of unsolicited communications that manipulate through urgency.

Unsolicited Requests: This can be through an email, phone call, or in-person request, each of which should always raise suspicion over the request of sensitive information. Most of these types of attackers will work under urgent terms to expedite the action without proper verification.

Use Strong Authentication Methods: Use MFA for added security. When the attacker gets your password, MFA blocks unauthorized access.

Keep Software Up-to-Date: Keep updating your software as you do for antivirus software. The software would, in turn, be able to cope with recent threats and vulnerabilities through periodic updates.

Enforce Strong Security Policy: An organization should set sound security policies about access controls, data classification, and periodic audits on security.

Threat Monitoring and Response: Make use of monitoring systems against malicious activities and response to the same. Quicker detection and quicker responses mean lesser damage by any social engineering attack.

Conclusion

Social engineering attacks are some of the most insidious forms of cyber threats, since they will leverage human psychology to carry out their attacks. A much deeper understanding of the various forms they take and comprehensively defensive strategies against them lowers your chances of being the next social engineering victim by a great order of magnitude. Remember, awareness, skepticism, and good security practices will be the keys to defense.

Above is a result of research articles Salahdine & Kaabouch, 2019; Krombholz et al., 2015; Gupta, Singhal, & Kapoor, 2016 gives you much better awareness about the methodologies and also the countermeasures concerning social engineering attacks. Be aware-be secure!

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